

was incorporated into the soil. Urea was topdressed in equal splits at 10, 45, and 75 days after IR2053-206-1-3-6 rice emerged. Weeds and water were controlled throughout the growing season.

At harvest, 50 panicles were randomly collected from each plot and number of filled grains per panicle and grain weight were recorded. The number of panicles per square meter was determined

for five 1-m rows randomly selected from each plot, and the center 3×7 m of each plot was harvested to determine grain yield. Data obtained over the three seasons were analyzed.

The results (see table) indicate that grain yield and all major yield components significantly and progressively increased with increased nitrogen application ($P < 0.001$). Interrow 20-cm spacing

produced higher grain yield than the other spacings used ($P < 0.001$). However, the close spacing produced more panicles/m², but fewer grains per panicle. Similarly, the 150 kg/ha seed rate produced more panicles per square meter but less grains per panicle. The differences in grain yield between the seeding rates were not significant. □

Environment and its influence

Panicle transpiration measurement with a potometer

O. S. Namuco, Agronomy Department; D. P. Garrity, International Rice Testing Program; and J. C. O'Toole, Agronomy Department, IRRI

Several studies on rice plant-water relationships have indicated the importance of panicle contribution to total plant water use during the flowering/heading stage.

A simple, inexpensive, rapid method, using a potometer, was used to estimate the transpiration rate of excised panicles. The potometer is portable and can be used in the field or laboratory (Fig. 1). Panicles were excised under water to prevent cavitation of the water column in the xylem by air bubbles. They were sealed into the potometer with parafilm and silicone sealant.

Potometers were placed under a fluorescent-incandescent light bank, which provided about $405 \mu\text{Em}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$ irradiance at the top of the panicle. Air velocity was maintained at 1.9ms^{-1} and passed uniformly through 4×4 cm baffles. Panicle temperature was measured by inserting copper-constantan thermocouples into the spikelets. A shielded-aspirated psychrometer was used to measure water vapor pressure deficit of the air. Water uptake, which should be in equilibrium with transpiration in a steady state system, was determined by changes in the level of meniscus in the pipette measured at 15-minute intervals. To refill the pipette, water was injected through the surgical tubing using a hypodermic needle. The pipette was covered

1. A potometer setup for measurement of panicle transpiration.

2. Water uptake of excised IR36 panicles measured with a potometer. Vapor pressure deficit of the air = 1.652 ± 0.0196 kPa, panicle temperature = $24.21 \pm .062^\circ\text{C}$.

with aluminum foil to prevent expansion of water caused by heating from the light source. After several water uptake readings, panicle area was measured with an automatic area meter. Transpiration was

estimated based on the area of exposed surfaces and on oven-dry weight. Results from both estimates (Fig. 2) showed that the cumulative water uptake or transpiration was linear.

This simple, inexpensive technique should be useful for studying the effects of environmental factors on water use by panicles and for investigations of genotypic variation in panicle water use. □

Rice-based cropping systems

Krishnamany — a new cowpea variety for the summer rice fallow

P. Chandrika, N. Rajappan Nair, T. K. Viswanathan, and J. Sreekumari Amma, Raional Agricultural Research Station, Pakmbi 679 306, Kerala, India

Nearly 80,000 ha in Kerala have potential for increasing pulse production during summer rice fallow. The Government of Kerala is encouraging cowpea production. Harvesting cowpea is expensive because plants must be picked four or five times. A new cowpea variety, Krishnamany, has a very short flowering phase and requires only one or two pickings. It also withstands moisture stress, which is normal during the post-summer period.

Krishnamany is a black-seeded selec-

Performance of Kdnamany in summer rice fallow in Kerala, India

Variety	Seed yield (kg/ha)						
	Pattambi			Mannuthy	Karamana	Mean	per day
	1980	1981	1982	1982	1982		
Krishnamany	472	719	666	1118	602	715	13.75
Culture 17	465	693	664	1048	513	677	13.02
P. 118	133	323	503	840	250	410	6.95
Kolinji payar	435	478	479	1158	355	581	9.85
Pusa phalguni	402	581	444	790	243	492	8.34
EC 43721	310	576	567	830	306	518	8.78
CD (P = 0.05)	238	137	160	N. S.	160	—	—

tion from P. 118/Kolinjipayar. It has short duration (55-60 days), is bushy and nontrading, grows 30-35 cm tall, and produces 2-5 branches. Flowers are light violet and medium sized. Pods are about 11 cm long, dark green when immature,

and light brown when dry. There are about 10 seeds per pod, which weigh 70 g/1000. The variety is tolerant of yellow mosaic. Recommended seed rate is 20 kg/ha, with 20-30-10 kg NPK/ha. Performance data are in the table. □

Rice — wheat pattern for increased cereal production in alkali soils of eastern Uttar Pradesh

T. N. Singh, Crop Physiology Department, N. D. University of Agriculture and Technology, Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

Although much of eastern Uttar Pradesh is planted to cereals, production is low

because of alkaline soils. A rice — wheat cropping pattern was tested in alkali fields at the Kumarganj Crop Research Station from 1976 to 1978.

Soil was 54% sand, 22.3% silt, and 22.1% clay. CEC was 13.4 meq/100 g, ESP 81.6, pH 10.4, EC 2.1 mmho/cm in 1:2 soil:water suspension at 0-15 cm soil depth. Three replications of 5 × 4 m plots in a randomized block design were

established and soil was treated with 0, 3, 6, 9, and 12 t gypsum/ha or 0, 1.5, 3, 4.5, and 6 t pyrite/ha before the first transplanting. Less pyrite was applied because it contains 50% more sulfur than gypsum and is almost twice as expensive. Rice husk was applied with gypsum, and sawdust with pyrite at 0, 2.5, 5, and 7.5 t/ha. Dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*) was grown and incorporated as green manure

Cereal grain production from rice — wheat crop sequence in alkali soils at Kumarganj, Faizabad, India

Application rate of soil amendments in 1976 (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)							
	1976-77		1977-78		1978-79		3-year average	
	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat
Gypsum								
0	1.0	1.0	1.6	1.1	2.0	1.1	1.5	1.1
3	2.0	2.4	2.9	2.1	3.4	2.1	2.8	2.2
6	3.5	3.4	4.6	3.0	4.7	2.9	4.3	3.1
9	4.8	4.3	6.0	3.7	6.2	3.6	5.7	3.9
12	5.3	4.8	6.4	4.2	6.8	4.2	6.2	4.4
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3

CONTINUED ON NEXT PAGE